

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Efficacy of Monitoring and Evaluation Function in Achieving Project Success in Kenya: A Survey of County Government's Projects

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Abstract

This paper sets out to examine the efficacy of monitoring and evaluation in achieving project success in Kenya. The victory of project management is usually gauged by the project success. Project success is achieved as a result of various contributing factors. One of the major factors leading to project success is monitoring and evaluation. This study therefore examined the efficiency of monitoring and evaluation function and its effect in achieving project success. This was done by assessing whether various attributes monitoring and evaluation such as; strength of monitoring, monitoring approach adopted, political influence and project lifecycle stage affects project success. Each of these attributes was regressed against the project success. The study found out that all the monitoring and evaluation attributes assessed had some impact in achieving the Project success. This study concluded that a number of projects that fail were as a result of weak a monitoring and evaluation function which was partly contributed by lack of management support. The study contributed new knowledge in that it established that projects may be unsuccessful despite having monitoring and evaluation function due to the weakness of M&E, lack of management support on the project functions, and political interference especially in Africa and developing countries.

Keywords: *Monitoring and Evaluation, Project Success, Kenya, County Governments.*

Introduction

Project management has gained focus lately. Most managers are embracing project management as a tool for achieving business objectives. The victory of project management is usually gauged by the project success. Project success is achieved as a result of various contributing factors. One of the major factors leading to project success is monitoring and evaluation. There seems to be a consensus by various scholars that monitoring and evaluation is one of the contributing factors to project success. This notwithstanding, there are several reports that a number of projects have also failed, despite having an M&E function within itself.

This study was on efficacy of monitoring and evaluation in achieving project success in Kenya. The study addresses the research problem that; despite existence of a monitoring and evaluation function in most projects, there are still project failures. The research found out that project success (or lack of it) was attributable to efficiency of monitoring and evaluation function. This thesis is divided into five chapters. This chapter covers the background of study, research problem, research objective, research questions, and

significance of the study, limitations and operational definitions.

Background of the Study

Monitoring is defined as “a continuous assessment aiming at providing all stakeholders, with early detailed information on the progress or delay of the ongoing assessed activity” [1]. Further World Bank [2] defined monitoring as a “continuing function that aims primarily to provide the management and main stakeholders of an ongoing intervention with early indications of progress, or lack thereof, in the achievement of results”. According to World Bank, regular collection of information through continuous monitoring assist project managers in making timely decisions, guarantee accountability, and provide the basis for evaluation and learning. According to Bamberger [3], monitoring is a type of evaluation performed when the project is being implemented and the data obtained through monitoring is made use of in evaluation. The purpose of carrying out monitoring is to enhance accountability by management on the resources employed and the results achieved and to make informed decisions on the project.

World Bank [2] defined evaluation as “the systematic and objective assessment of an on-going or completed project, program, or policy, and its design, implementation and results”. The aim of evaluation is to determine the relevance and fulfillment of objectives, development efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability. According to World Bank, an effective evaluation should provide information that is plausible and helpful, enabling the integration of lessons learned into the decision making process of both project management and financiers. Evaluation can also be described as “a systematic and objective examination concerning the relevance, effectiveness, efficiency and impact of activities in the light of specified objectives” [1]. A good evaluation process helps the project managers to draw conclusions about relevance, value, competence, impact and sustainability of a project and is carried out at various stages of project implementation.

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) is described as a process that assists project managers in improving performance and achieving results. The goal of M&E is to improve current and future management of outputs, outcomes and impact [1]. Generally, monitoring can be said to be connected to evaluation, as such information obtained from previous monitoring processes can be used during evaluation process. This research does not make a distinction between monitoring and evaluation; it combines the two into one concept for easier data collection and analysis.

Project management has received attention in the past few decades. Project Management Book of Common Knowledge [4] defines project management as the “application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to project activities to meet the project requirements.” Project Management Book Of common Knowledge (PMBOK) further explains that project management is accomplished through “the appropriate application and integration of the various processes which are grouped into Initiating, Planning, Executing, Monitoring and Controlling, and Closing”. These stages are commonly referred to as the project lifecycle by the project management theory.

PMBOK also highlights various factors that may lead to project success which includes: creating right teams; involving stakeholders; preparation of detailed project scope; influence on the stakeholders; information; managing expectations; communication; negotiation; and monitoring and evaluation. This therefore implies

that monitoring and evaluation is one of the critical factors to project success. Equally, several studies have been carried out focusing on the project success. For example Raymond & Bergeron [5] identified several indicators of project success identified in the literature including “reduction of the time required to complete a task, improved control of activity costs, better management of budgets, improved planning of activities, better monitoring of activities, more efficient resource allocation, and better monitoring of the project schedule”. Project success is defined by various scholars on the basis of delivery of all or most of what it said it would (the scope); delivery of scope on schedule and/or within the agreed budget; delivery to the expected quality standards; achievement of project objectives; and most importantly the creation of significant net value for the organization after the project completion [6-9].

Mbeche [10] adds to the list of critical success factors which includes financial viability and management, market analysis and management and the quality of project management. These factors are important during project preparation and project implementation. According to PMBOK [4], in order for the project managers to achieve project success, they need to monitor and control the processes of producing the products, services or results that the project was undertaken to produce. Chan et’al [11] groups project success factors into five main categories which are “Project Management actions, project-related factors, project procedures, human-related factors and external environment”. These project success factors needs to be monitored constantly for the project to achieve success in terms of value creation. The last phase of the Project Risk Management Loop of Control is monitoring as expressed by Burke [12] is documenting monitoring risks in order to ensure proper action for prevention. Similarly in project management documentation of monitoring risks is also critical in the achievement of project success.

Monitoring and evaluation is a key component in projects and it is one of the critical success factors as explained in the previous paragraphs. Despite the presence of monitoring and evaluation function, Pretorius et’al [9] in a study established that majority of projects sampled were perceived by the respondents as successful. The success of projects was attributed to the factors such as good “scope management, time management, cost management, quality management and human relations management”. Monitoring and evaluation during all the stages of project lifecycle

can be employed in order to reduce instances of unsuccessful projects in developing countries, including Kenya.

Several projects in Kenya are termed as “white elephants”, a term that is commonly used to denote failed projects. The failed big projects signed by the government includes a fertilizer plant in Mombasa, maize cob processing factory in Eldoret and a molasses plant in Kisumu. On the other hand there are projects that were strongly opposed by some politicians but eventually turned out to be productive, for example the construction of an oil pipeline from Mombasa to Nairobi [13,14]. Other than politics other factors also influence project success.

The issue of gender in Kenya for example is also a contributing factor to project success if well handled. According to Warren and Susan [15] in their study, a “project in Kenya”, which sought to organize a co-operative society to generate income from the sale of the flowers, failed when women reduced their participation to protest the fact that men were the only ones who received payment?” Effective monitoring and evaluation would play a vital role in detecting the signs of project failure and hence suggesting corrective actions that may be necessary.

Another study carried out in Kenya indicated that “the organizations’ projects had adequate number of supervising staff and that project teams used work schedules and plans to monitor project implementation”. The study also concluded that supervision capacity has a significant influence on the successful completion of projects [16]. This study corroborates with the other studies that monitoring and evaluation is critical to project success even in Kenya.

According to a research by Ika [17] projects in Africa faces problems which can be categorized into any of the four traps namely: “the one-size-fits-all technical trap, the accountability-for-results trap, the lack-of-project-management-capacity trap, and the cultural trap”. The study suggests increase in supervision and monitoring efforts as one of the actions that should be taken to avoid some of the traps. This implies that the projects in Africa often fail due to lack of effective monitoring and evaluation.

Several legislations in Kenya such as the Public Service Commission Act, the Public Procurement and Disposal Act, and the Constitution of Kenya 2010, create demand for M&E and emphasizes on accountability and transparency from public institutions [18]. Entrenching monitoring and

evaluation in the law attempts to make it mandatory for all the public projects. The main question is whether the mandatory M & E is working effectively given a number of white elephants in the country in the recent past. Creation of the 47 counties, responsible of their own development and projects financing, has indeed increased the need for Monitoring and evaluation and Project Management services at the county level [18].

Kontinen and Robinson [19] identified Lack of monitoring tools, difficulty in defining performance indicators and short time allocation to M & E as some of the challenges that constantly face the project monitoring function. When M & E faces various challenges, its effectiveness is at stake hence impacting on the project success.

Monitoring and evaluation exercise involves data collection and processing. Traditional control systems are characterized by “manual data collection, improper data sharing, and the gap between monitoring and control usually result in late identification of deviations in project performance” [20]. An effective monitoring and activity is one that identifies deviations in a timely manner and provides feedback appropriately; hence enhancing the chances of project success. In Kenya M & E is not automated. This may lead to delays in data collection and analysis.

Further studies have been carried out to explore the possibilities of improving the productivity of projects by automating project monitoring and control. This will enable automatic data capturing and processing based on the actual project performance. Nonetheless, the studies also indicate that certain manually obtained data is still important in addition to the automatically collected data [21]. Since full automation of M & E process may not be practically possible, it may be difficult to fully eliminate the problem of delays in detecting the variances.

Managers risk wasting monitoring resources as a result of poor planning. Failing to effectively plan for monitoring and evaluation may lead to its ineffectiveness and in efficiency, which has a cost implication. Effective monitoring and evaluation helps in providing timely information on the project progress which in turn leads to increase in technical capacity and project success [22]. Ineffective monitoring and evaluation leads to wastage of resources and has a negative effect on the project success.

In a nutshell, over the recent several decades, organizations have greatly increased their use of projects to achieve business objectives. During this period project management researchers have been trying to discover the factors lead to project success [23-28] and have reached various conclusions that have been widely reflected in literature written by project management practitioners. An increasing number of studies [6,8, 29,30] have identified monitoring and evaluation as one of the key factors contributing to the project success. Moreover, a number of projects in the world have been reported as over budgeted, late, or are simply not good enough which means that they are unsuccessful. Still, different scholars claim that those projects have been successful depending on the perspective [8]. This conflict in literature brings about a dilemma that though several researchers agree that monitoring and evaluation leads to project success, yet there are several projects which do not succeed, perhaps with or without the monitoring function in place. This therefore raises doubt as to whether the monitoring and evaluation exercise was effective enough to add value to the projects operations.

Problem Statement

The success of projects plays a key role in achieving organization growth and development. Most project managers appreciate that monitoring and evaluation of projects is important if the project objectives and success is to be achieved. Project monitoring and evaluation exercise adds value to the overall efficiency of project planning, management and implementation by offering corrective action to the variances from the expected standard. "Project managers are required to undertake more rigorous monitoring and evaluation of the projects and develop frameworks and guidelines for measuring impact" [31]. By so doing they will achieve greater value creation for the organization through project success.

Studies carried out in Kenya shows that quite a number of projects have been successful. For example, The Youth Enterprise Development Fund; whose objective was to increase economic opportunities for the youth as a way of enabling them to participate in nation building [32]; the self reliant agriculture (SRA) projects which were meant to help the villagers become self reliant by growing their own food. This program was viewed as successful since it realized its goals through training local population of Mnyenzi on how to raise their own food. Most of the villagers had

access to land where they could plant gardens and raise animals but the land was not used efficiently [33]. On the other hand, several projects in Kenya have been informally cited as failed projects; meaning that they did not achieve the desired success. Examples of such projects include the Kibera slum upgrading project, the Lake Turkana fish processing plant project, The Anglo-leasing ICT related projects, Modambogo Health Center in rain water harvesting Mwatate, and Tumaini Women Self Help group project in Kisumu among others. Some of the studies show that one of the drawbacks of monitoring and evaluation in Kenya is failure by the management to implement the recommendations offered by the M&E team [34]. In Africa including Kenya, project management is also complicated by some factors such as lack of skills in project management, political and community or societal demands.

A significant share of the failed projects was government funded or donor funded projects. These projects usually undergo the necessary monitoring and evaluation processes which are often a requirement of the law. The paradox is, despite a consensus among scholars that proper monitoring and evaluation leads to project success, there are still cases of project failure in Kenya. Further projects fail despite heavy presence of monitoring and evaluation activities. This therefore raises serious issues as to whether the monitoring and evaluation employed is effective enough to achieve project success. The monitoring team perhaps may be lacking the necessary capacity or strength to carry out their work effectively, or they may be approaching their work using incorrect methodologies. The project monitoring team may also be lacking the necessary management support. This thesis examined the efficacy of monitoring and evaluation in achieving project success in Kenya. The findings of the study attempted to provide a solution to the stated Problem

Methodology

The research targeted a sample of 217 projects in Bungoma that were budgeted for and undertaken during the financial year 2013/14. Interviews were conducted and questionnaires distributed to 206 project monitoring officers. The 7 projects were not implemented as budgeted and hence could not be included in the survey. The researcher could not access 4 of the projects due to their locality; the projects were located in the extreme locations of the county making their accessibility difficult more so because of the rough

terrain. The response rate represents 94.9% of the originally targeted sample, which the researcher believed is sufficient for the study.

The following Research model was tested using multiple regression analysis.

$$PS = \alpha + \beta_1 * SM + \beta_2 * MA + \beta_3 * LCS + \beta_4 * PI + \epsilon$$

Where $PS = Project\ success$
 $SM = Strength\ of\ Monitoring$
 $MA = Monitoring\ approach$
 $LCS = Life\ cycled\ stage$
 $PI = Political\ Influence$
 $\epsilon = Error\ term$

Research Findings and Discussions

The data collected was analyzed and the results were as recorded in the subsequent sub sections

Project Success

The weighted average mean was calculated using the responses from variables explained in the subsections above. More weight was given to customer satisfaction from projects, organizational objectives, quality aspects while fewer weights were assigned to time and cost factors.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics-project Success

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Project Success	206	3.6375	1.09010	.07595

Table 1 above shows a weighted mean of 3.64 which is above the average mark of 3.0. This generally means that more than half of the projects implemented in the county were perceived to be successful.

Strength of Monitoring and Evaluation Team

The weighted average mean was calculated using the responses from variables explained in the subsections above. More weight was given Stakeholders representation, M&E recommendations taken seriously, M&E team skills and teamwork while fewer weights were assigned to facilitation of M&E teams, regular meetings and size of the team.

Table 2 above shows a weighted mean of 3.20 which is above the average mark of 3.0. This generally means that more than half of the monitoring and evaluation teams were perceived to be strong.

Table 2 : Descriptive statistics – strength of M&E team

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Strength of M&E team	206	3.2039	1.18025	.08223

This is in agreement with the observation of Laohavichien et al., that leaders strengthen a team for reduce conflicts among team members and to increase organizational performance.

Monitoring and Evaluation Methods Applied

Respondents were required to select a number of monitoring and evaluation approaches or techniques that they employed. The results were as recorded in figure 4.16 below where accounting and certification was identified as the most frequently used approach (36%) followed closely by a related method referred to as status assessment at 33.7%. These two methods have taken the lead because most of the projects under this research were constructions in nature and requires status assessments from time to time for the purposes of paying the contractor. Basic research was selected by 14.6% of the respondents while objectives evaluation and/or value for money assessment were chosen by 12.4% of the respondents. The two methods are basic but were not being applied extensively as the case should be. This is perhaps because of lack of involvement of internal audit department in the monitoring teams. This could also be attributed to lack of knowledge on how to use the two techniques in monitoring and evaluation of projects. The last two techniques to be selected included earned value analysis and effectiveness measurements at 2.2% and 1.1% respectively. This implies that the two techniques were not well understood by the county monitoring teams and hence not commonly applied. Finally two modern techniques which the researcher felt were very instrumental in achieving meaningful evaluations of the projects were not being applied at all. These two techniques were balanced score card approach and the log frame matrix.

Reasons for Not Using Log Frame Matrix Approach

The respondents who did not apply log frame matrix as one of their evaluation techniques were required to state the reasons why they were not using it. Several options were given for them to select the ones that apply to them.

Figure 1: M&E approach/ techniques

Since no respondent who indicated that they used log frame matrix, the reasons cited then applies to all the respondents and by extension all the M&E teams in the county government. Lack of awareness by the organizations management was cited by the highest number of respondents (33%) as a reason for not using log frame matrix approach. A related reason, lack of awareness by project managers, was rated at 27% of responses. These two related reasons account for 60% of the responses which means that lack of knowledge on the log frame technique was clearly a major contributor to its non-use. This implies that if training is carried out about the modern evaluation techniques, M&E team members may eventually use them as part of their evaluation approaches. The second highest voted reason was that log frame matrix was not mandatory for the organization. This means that since it was not a

requirement of the law or any other regulation, the M&E teams found it not necessary to apply the method in their work. 5% of the responses attribute to non-use of log frame matrix to its being cumbersome, 2% stated that M&E teams do not take log frame matrix seriously and 1 % believes that log frame matrix is of less importance to the organization.

Most of the respondents believe that stakeholders are well represented in the monitoring and evaluation team. This could have been attributed to the quality of the capacity building undertaken by the various national government agencies like the Office of the President, visionary county leadership, and stakeholder participation in the other types of projects. The stakeholder good representation in the monitoring and evaluation team could also be attributed to the skills of all the stakeholders involved in project implementation.

Figure 2: Reasons for not using log frame matrix

Factors that Management/ M&E Team takes into Consideration when Choosing an Approach to be Used in Monitoring and Evaluation

The respondents were required to explain factors that management/ M&E team takes into consideration when choosing an approach to be used in monitoring and evaluation. Most of the respondents made comments on the

considerations made by management or M&E team in identifying the monitoring approach. The comments were analyzed with help of QSR-NVivo software and the main points identified by the respondents were classified into two groups i.e. project related factors and management related factors as illustrated in the following diagram.

Figure 3: Factors affecting the choice of M&E approach

Project Lifecycle Stages

Intensity of Monitoring and Evaluation Activities at Various Stages of Project Life Cycle

Respondents were required to indicate the level of agreement or disagreement on the intensity of M&E engagement at various stages of project life cycle.

Figure 4: Intensity of M&E as per project life cycle stages

Responses obtained were averaged and a graph plotted so as to study the pattern. The graph is interpreted to mean that less monitoring activities were required at the initial stages of the

project while a bulk of monitoring activities were necessary during project implementation. Lesser activities were required at the closing stage of project life cycle.

Inference from the responses confirms that the project life cycle is relevant to M & E if the project was to achieve success. M&E at the planning stages of projects assists the project managers in undertaking the necessary interventions and mitigations to be used in project implementation to ensure project continuity, project re-invention, project entry and exit strategies, and stakeholder project ownership participation in the other types of projects. M&E at implementation stage helps in monitoring the project performance, costs, time and scope. M&E at the closing stage is important in ensuring that the project is of good quality and meets minimum technical specifications, such that after handing over to the users, the project

will operate optimally. Project life cycle is key tool to be used to identify at which stage of growth a project has reached and which measures are to be taken to ensure project success.

Activities Carried Out During Various Stages

The respondents were required to explain “the monitoring activities that took place in your project during the various stages of project lifecycle.” Analysis of their responses using QSR NVivo helped in identifying various activities that usually takes place in various projects undertaken by the county government. The various activities are explained using the following diagram

Figure 5: Monitoring activities as per lifecycle stages

Political Interference with M&E

The weighted average mean was calculated using the responses from variables explained in the subsections above. More weight was given to interference by MCAs since they are spread throughout the county and their interference could be quite significant.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics – overall political interference

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Overall Political interference	206	2.6019	1.10290	.07684

Table 3 above shows a weighted mean of 2.60 which is below the average mark of 3.0. This generally means that the respondents perceived that political interference was less. This implies that the political class in the county was not over interfering with the monitoring and evaluation activities and by extension the project management. The results on the project success explained in earlier sections of this report

indicated that, generally the projects in the county under review were successful. Minimal interference from politicians could have greatly contributed to this success among the other factors studied.

Multiple Regression Analysis (Model Testing)

The multiple regression analysis models the linear relationship between the dependent variable which was project success and independent variables which were; strength of M&E team, M&E Approach adopted, project lifecycle stage and political influence. According to the results of the regression analysis, the independent variables explain 85.5% of project success (R²). The F-statistic (ANOVA) for the model was 295.6 which was significant at 5% level of significance (P-value was 0.000 which was less than 0.05). The regression analysis coefficients are as shown in 4 below.

The Coefficients table provides the necessary information to predict project success from

Strength of Monitoring Team, Monitoring Approach, Life Cycle stage and Political Influence,

Table 4: Model testing-multiple regression analysis

Model		Coefficients			t	Sig.
		Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.105	.234		-.450	.653
	Strength of Monitoring Team	.506	.041	.547	12.431	.000
	Monitoring Approach	.419	.050	.373	8.458	.000
	Life Cycle stage	.213	.053	.117	4.035	.000
	Political Influence	.015	.027	.015	.556	.579

a. Dependent Variable: Project Success : R² =0.855

as well as determine whether income Strength of Monitoring Team, Monitoring Approach, Life Cycle stage and Political Influence contributes statistically significantly to the model (by looking at the "Sig." column). Further, the researcher uses the values in the "B" column under the "Un-standardized Coefficients" column, as shown to present the regression equation as:

$$PS = -0.105 + 0.506 * SM + 0.419 * MA + 0.213 * LCS + 0.015 * PI + C$$

Expounded as follows:

$$\text{Project Success} = -0.105 + 0.506 (\text{Strength of Monitoring Team}) + 0.419 (\text{Monitoring Approach}) + 0.213 (\text{Life Cycle stage}) + 0.015 (\text{Political Influence})$$

This indicates that Strength of Monitoring Team had the highest influence on the project success by a coefficient of 0.506, followed by Monitoring Approach influences project success by a coefficient of 0.419, then by Life Cycle stage which influences project success by 0.213 while Political Influence influences project success by 0.015. It was observed that all the four variables had a positive effect on the project success.

Three variables which are Strength of Monitoring Team, Monitoring Approach, and Life Cycle stage were found to have a statistically significant effect on project success since their significance levels (from Table 4.21 above) were less than 0.05. On the other hand political interference was not a significant predictor of project success since significance level was more than 0.05. Each of the variables is explained in the subsequent paragraphs.

Y intercept of -1.05 is low, meaning that in absence of the other variables, the project success is very low. This is further confirmed by the significance levels which is more than 0.05. The

study therefore concludes that the Y-intercept in the above model is not a significant predictor of project success. The operations of the other variables have a great effect on the project success.

Strength of M&E team has a coefficient of 0.506 with a significance level of 0.000. This implies that the nature of the relationship between strength of M&E and project success is positive. The higher the strength of M&E team, the higher the project success and vice versa. The significance level is almost negligible meaning that strength of M&E is a significant factor contributing to project success.

M&E Approach has a coefficient of 0.419 with a significance level of 0.000. This implies that the nature of the relationship between auditor skills and audit expectation gap is positive. The better the M&E Approach, the higher the project success and vice versa. The significance level is almost negligible meaning that M&E Approach is a significant factor contributing to project success.

Project lifecycle stage has a coefficient of 0.213 with a significance level of 0.000. This implies that the nature of the relationship between Project lifecycle stage and project success is positive. Further the significance level indicates that the Project lifecycle stage is a significant factor contributing to project success. Finally political interference has a coefficient of 0.015 with a significance level of 0.579. This implies that the nature of the relationship between political interference and project success is positive. However the significance level indicates that the political interference is not a significant factor contributing to project success.

Goodness of Fit of the Model - ANOVA

The ANOVA test was run to test the goodness of fit of the model specified above. The results of the

goodness of fit of the regression model were as indicated in the Table 5

Table 5: ANOVA – model testing

Model	Sum of Squares	ANOVA ^a		F	Sig.	
		df	Mean Square			
1	Regression	208.215	4	52.054	295.658	.000 ^b
	Residual	35.388	201	.176		
	Total	243.603	205			

a. Dependent Variable: Project Success

b. Predictors: (Constant), Political Influence, Life Cycle stage, Monitoring Approach, Strength of Monitoring Team

The ANOVA table, which reports how well the regression equation fits the data (i.e., predicts the dependent variable). Table 4.22 indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly well. The “Sig.” column indicates the statistical significance of the regression model that was run. Here, $p < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05, and indicates that, overall, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (i.e., it is a good fit for the data) [35-37].

Conclusions

The key role of the M&E function is to provide the relevant feedback to the management so as to ensure that the project implementation is kept in check. In other words the M&E team is supposed to confirm to the project managers that the project is on course or not. The research problem that this report intended to address was that projects that fail usually have an M&E function. The question that was raised from the problem was whether the M&E function was effective in their working.

In addressing the research problem and hence answering the research question, this research gathered and analyzed data which has led to this conclusion. This research then concluded that generally projects implemented by the county government were successful. The success of these projects was as a result of strong M&E function within the relevant projects; a fair M&E approach

which produced a good feedback; closely monitoring the project at all stages in the project lifecycle and minimal political interference on the project management.

Management support was also a contributing factor to the success of project in the county. The management acted as a mediator between the project M&E function and project success. However some shortcomings were observed concerning the project success and monitoring approach. These shortcomings include; a number of projects were not completed on time; and a number of projects were also not completed within budget; this could be indicators of some weaknesses in project planning. Use of technology in monitoring and evaluation was scanty and this impacts on the timeliness of providing the monitoring reports. Another shortcoming that was observed was that the county is still relying on the traditional approaches to M&E and completely not using the modern approaches which are more holistic.

M&E function was found to be a significant factor which contributes to projects success. The research findings in this study suggest that projects can still fail despite having an M&E function. This would be as a result of a weakness in M&E, poor approach to M&E, lack of management support on the project functions, and political interference especially in Africa and developing countries. This was the main contribution to the body of knowledge in that it established that projects may be unsuccessful despite having M&E.

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